

CORD-MI study on care monitoring I: Kawasaki syndrome and PIMS

English translation of the description in the project register of the German Portal for Medical Research Data

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Project description

Kawasaki syndrome, also known as mucocutaneous lymph node syndrome, is an acute inflammation of the small and medium-sized blood vessels that usually affects small children between the ages of two and five. If left untreated, the coronary arteries can be severely damaged, possibly leading to a heart attack, bleeding or death. However, if Kawasaki syndrome is recognized and treated in time, the chance of survival is high. However, late effects, particularly on the heart, are possible. A new syndrome has been observed that is very similar to Kawasaki syndrome, PIMS (Pediatric Inflammatory Multisystem Syndrome), and is possibly related to SARS-CoV-2 infection. PIMS is also a severe and acute inflammatory disease in children. In 2020, the WHO has called for PIMS to be monitored and researched. The aim is to try to establish a link between PIMS or Kawasaki syndrome and a SARS-CoV-2 infection and to obtain data on its frequency and spread.

Project details

Project goals

The study is being conducted to answer the following research questions based on retrospective health data:

- How often is Kawasaki syndrome or PIMS documented over time?
- How often is Kawasaki syndrome or PIMS documented in combination with a positive COVID-19 result?
- Does the frequency of Kawasaki syndrome or PIMS differ regionally in Germany?
- Does the frequency of Kawasaki syndrome or PIMS differ between the sexes and age groups?

Scientific background

Kawasaki syndrome (KS) is the most common form of generalized vasculitis in children aged 0-5 years. The first case was described in Japan in 1960 and in Germany in 1979. Due to its effects on the coronary vessels, KS leads to considerable morbidity and mortality. In 2016, the incidence in Germany was 7.2 cases per 100,000 inhabitants [1]. For Europe, an incidence of 1/6,500-20,500 is reported in children under 5 years of age. KS is therefore a rare disease. In recent years, a more sensitive case definition and improved diagnostics have been demonstrated [2]. The current incidence of CS during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in Italy and the USA is significantly higher than in comparable periods in the previous year. However, since SARS-CoV-2 infections are in addition to the usual seasonal viral infections, it is currently unclear whether SARS-CoV-2 infections contribute disproportionately to a hyperinflammatory syndrome in the temporal context of the pandemic.

In the context of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, an accumulation of hyperinflammatory syndromes in children has been described since April 2020, which have been summarized under the acronyms PIMS and MIS-C. PIMS partially or fully fulfills the criteria for Kawasaki syndrome [3]. However, of 230 reported cases in the European Union and the United Kingdom, most children were between 7 and 16 years old and thus generally older than children presenting with classic Kawasaki syndrome [4].

The first data on a hyperinflammatory syndrome as a delayed (more than 7-10 days after infection) increased immune response in connection with a SARS-CoV-2 infection in children make it necessary to establish a valid epidemiological data situation on frequency and spread, since direct proof of a connection to a SARS-CoV-2 infection is often no longer possible due to the delayed onset.

Literature

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- RCPCH, 2020. Paediatric multisystem inflammatory syndrome temporally associated with COVID-19 (PIMS) - guidance for clinicians. Royal College of Paediatrics and Child Health, London.
- ISS COVID-19 Rare Diseases Working Group, 2020. Interim guidance on Kawasaki disease and acute multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children and adolescents in the current emergency scenario of SARS-CoV-2 infection (No. Rapporto ISS COVID-19, nn. 29/2020-English version). Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Roma.

Material and methods

In the case of Kawasaki syndrome and PIMS, a case-based evaluation of the data with hospitalized children with KS and PIMS is carried out. The first step is to identify the cases at each location in which the diagnosis of Kawasaki syndrome (M30.3) or PIMS (D76.1-4, A48.3, R57.8, R65.0-9, D89.8/9) was coded.

The study is conducted decentrally, with the data initially evaluated separately at each location by running centrally developed analysis scripts at the individual locations. Only the anonymous total figures are then combined centrally. As anonymity cannot be guaranteed for a total number at a location above 0 but below 6, the corresponding figures are reported as category "1 to 5". As a result, the sensitive patient data remains at the sites, but can still be used for research while maintaining privacy.

Project result

14 locations participated in the data delivery in order to answer the research questions. Individual results are highlighted separately below. A comprehensive scientific analysis is currently underway. Kawasaki syndrome and PIMS in connection with COVID-19 findings: Looking at the link between Kawasaki syndrome or PIMS and a COVID-19 diagnosis, it is clear that the vast majority of PIMS patients had a previous COVID-19 diagnosis. This was not always the case for patients coded as having Kawasaki syndrome. Over the course of the pandemic, the quality of the coding or the coding itself may also have changed due to increasing knowledge about PIMS. For example, the ICD code U10.9 was newly introduced for PIMS in 2021, while in previous years (including 2020) the inflammatory syndrome was coded as U07.5. The connection between Kawasaki syndrome or PIMS and COVID-19 detection was to be expected. The study by the German Society for Pediatric Infectiology (DGPI), which investigated PIMS cases in Germany, also showed that the clinical pictures of Kawasaki syndrome and the "new" inflammatory syndrome PIMS were mixed during the pandemic, which did not always make a clear classification possible.

Data providers involved

- Charité - University Medicine Berlin
- Johann Wolfgang Goethe University Frankfurt am Main / University Hospital Frankfurt
- Otto-von-Guericke University Magdeburg / University Hospital Magdeburg
- Philipps University Marburg / University Hospital Giessen / Marburg
- TU Dresden / University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus Dresden
- University of Münster / University Hospital Münster
- University Hospital Aachen
- University Hospital Erlangen
- Heidelberg University Hospital
- University Hospital Cologne
- University Hospital Regensburg
- University Hospital Tübingen
- Ulm University Hospital
- University Hospital Würzburg